

Heterocarboxylates of Lanthanones

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Reactions of lanthanide isopropoxides with heterocarboxylic acids in different molar ratios have been carried out in anhydrous benzene yielding insoluble products of the type $Y(OPr^i)_{3-x}(OCOR)_x$ ($\bar{O}COR$ is the anion of the furan-2-carboxylic acid or thiophene-2-carboxylic acid), and $Ln(OCOR)_3$ ($Ln=Pr, Nd, Sm, Dy$ or Ho and $\bar{O}COR$ is the anion of 5-bromofuran-2-carboxylic acid). These derivatives were powdery, with colour characteristic of trivalent state of corresponding lanthanide ion, decompose above 200° without melting, and insoluble in common organic solvents. The ir spectra have also been discussed.

A considerable amount of work is reported on the aliphatic and aromatic hydroxy, amino, halogen substituted and thiocarboxylic acid derivatives of lanthanide elements¹⁻⁴ but very little work is published on the heterocarboxylates of lanthanide elements.

The present paper deals with the preparation of furan-2-carboxylic (FH), 5-bromofuran-2-carboxylic (BrFH) and thiophene-2-carboxylic (TH) acid derivatives of yttrium and 5-bromofuran-2-carboxylic acid derivatives of Pr, Nd, Sm, Dy and Ho as a result of the reaction between above mentioned lanthanide isopropoxides and the corresponding heterocarboxylic acid in anhydrous benzene and characterisation of the products.

Experimental

Stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture from apparatus and chemicals. Lanthanide isopropoxides were prepared by the sodium alkoxide method⁵. Lanthanide contents were estimated by ignition to sesquioxide. Bromine was estimated as AgBr and sulphur as BaSO₄. Isopropanol was estimated by oxidation with 1 N dichromate solution in 12.5% sulphuric acid⁶. Infrared spectra in KBr pellets were run on a Perkin Elmer 180 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the complexes: The procedure essentially involved the mixing of lanthanide isopropoxide and heterocarboxylic acids in anhydrous benzene (~60 ml) and refluxing over a fractionating column. The isopropanol liberated in the reaction was collected azeotropically with benzene. The products were rendered free of solvent by distillation under reduced pressure and finally dried at room temperature at reduced pressure for ~3 hr.

Results and Discussion

Lanthanide isopropoxides were treated with appropriate heterocarboxylic acids in different stoichiometric ratios in boiling benzene yielding products of the general formula $Ln(OPr^i)_{3-x}(OCOR)_x$ where Ln is Pr, Nd, Sm, Dy, Ho or Y and OCOR

is the anion of any of the above heterocarboxylic acids. These reactions are exothermic, facile and gave products in almost quantitative yields, and can be represented by the following general equation:

where x is 1, 2 or 3 and RCOOH is FH, TH or BrFH.

Reactions of lanthanide isopropoxide (Pr, Nd, Sm, Dy and Ho) with 5-bromofuran-2-carboxylic acid were carried out in the molar ratio of 1 : 3 only when, as a result of exothermic reactions, *tris*-derivatives were obtained. These compounds are fine powders having colour characteristic of the trivalent state of the corresponding lanthanide ion and are extremely soluble in dimethylformamide (DMF) or dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) but insoluble in benzene, methanol or chloroform. Most of these compounds do not melt below 200° but decompose with melting at higher temperature.

IR spectra of heterocarboxylates of lanthanones: The strong $\nu C-O$ band in the free furan-2-carboxylic acid (1685 cm^{-1}), thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (1679 cm^{-1}) and 5-bromofuran-2-carboxylic acid (1670 cm^{-1})⁷ splits into asym. and sym. OCO^- vibrations in these complexes and the band assignments of the spectra are given in Table 1.

The bidentate coordination of the carboxylate groups to the metal results in a lowering of both the νOCO^- stretching frequencies, due to the drainage of electron density from the carboxylate group to the metal. At the same time, the $O-C-O$ angle is expected to decrease when the metal oxygen bond becomes stronger. Decrease in the $O-C-O$ angle results in a decrease in the frequency separation $\Delta\nu$ ($\sim 125\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which suggests that the bonding of the carboxylate group to the metal is bidentate in *tris*-heterocarboxylates.

All the acid derivative showed the usual 2-substituted furan⁷ and thiophene⁸ ir vibrations with the ring breathing mode in the region $1012-1010$ (FH), $860-858$ (TH) and $1015-1010$ (BrFH) cm^{-1} , respectively. The ring breathing vibrations of furan,

TABLE I—PREPARATION AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF HETEROCARBOXYLATES OF LANTHANONES(III)

Reactants (Molar ratio)	Product (yield, g)	2-Propanol in azeotrope (g) Found (Calcd.)	Metal % Found (Calcd.)	Bromine % Found (Calcd.)	Decomp. Temp. °C	Assignments	
						asy OCO-	sym OCO-
Y(OPr ^t) ₃ , FH 1.22 0.52(1 : 1)	Y(OPr ^t) ₃ (F) (1.47)	0.27 (0.28)	27.34 (27.94)	—	245	1570 sh	1465 s
1.11 0.93(1 : 2)	Y(OPr ^t) ₃ (F) ₂ (1.54)	0.49 (0.50)	23.89 (24.01)	—	265-70	1540 sh	1465 s
1.22 1.53(1 : 3)	Y(F) ₃ (1.91)	0.81 (0.83)	20.67 (21.06)	—	300-305	1540 sh	1460 s
Y(OPr ^t) ₃ , TH 1.25 0.60(1 : 1)	Y(OPr ^t) ₃ (T) (1.56)	0.27 (0.28)	25.65 (25.59)	—	310-15	1570 sh 1555 s 1540 sh	1470 s 1440 s
0.87 0.84(1 : 2)	Y(OPr ^t) ₃ (T) ₂ (1.30)	0.39 (0.39)	21.29 (22.09)	—	325-30	1560 s 1540 sh	1465 sh 1455 s
1.73 2.50(1 : 3)	Y(T) ₃ (3.00)	1.16 (1.17)	18.42 (18.90)	—	335-40	1580 mbr	1465 vs
Y(OPr ^t) ₃ , BrFH 1.47 1.06(1 : 1)	Y(OPr ^t) ₃ (BrF) (2.14)	0.33 (0.33)	22.71 (22.38)	20.00 (20.12)	240-45	1590 s 1560 s	1470 s
1.11 1.60(1 : 2)	Y(OPr ^t) ₃ (BrF) ₂ (2.15)	0.49 (0.50)	16.42 (16.83)	30.11 (30.26)	250	1590 s 1560 s	1470 s
1.42 3.05(1 : 3)	Y(BrF) ₃ (3.41)	0.95 (0.96)	13.15 (13.49)	36.17 (36.38)	260-65	1590 s 1560 w	1465 s 1460 sh
Pr(OPr ^t) ₃ 0.38 0.68(1 : 3)	Pr(BrF) ₃	0.20 (0.21)	19.60 (19.82)	11.20 (11.24)	210-15		
Nd(OPr ^t) ₃ 0.92 1.64(1 : 3)	Nd(BrF) ₃	0.50 (0.51)	20.18 (20.20)	11.02 (11.18)	245-50		
Sm(OPr ^t) ₃ 0.27 0.47(1 : 3)	Sm(BrF) ₃	0.14 (0.14)	20.76 (20.87)	11.06 (11.09)	250-55		
Dy(OPr ^t) ₃ 0.47 0.80(1 : 3)	Dy(BrF) ₃ (1.02)	0.24 (0.25)	21.87 (22.18)	10.83 (10.91)	320-25		
Ho(OPr ^t) ₃ 0.33 0.55(1 : 3)	Ho(BrF) ₃ (0.71)	0.17 (0.17)	22.63 (22.44)	10.75 (10.87)	280-85		

FH=2-Furoic acid ; BrFH=5-Bromofuran-2-carboxylic acid ; TH=2-Thenoic acid.

thiophene and 5-bromofuran ring do not show any appreciable positive shift in these derivatives and occur almost at the same positions as in free acids indicating that the hetero oxygen or sulphur is not involved in the coordination.

The absorption bands in the region 680-400 cm⁻¹ are assigned to metal-oxygen stretching vibration⁹.

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